

“To Comparative Study of E-Banking, Kotak and Icici Bank”

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ABSTRACT:

Internet banking is dynamical the industry, having the key effects on banking relationships. In true web banking facilitates ‘anywhere anytime banking’ to its customers. Customers wish to access the net banking services because it is convenient and time over whelming. Customer’s victimization web banking doesn’t seem to be solely from the urban areas however conjointly from the agricultural areas. Where web banking offers relief to the shoppers at a similar time it provides cut to the banks by eradicating physical documentation. This analysis paper has as long as the internet banking is gaining quality among customers because of its varied advantages like ease and convenience, quick and higher services, user friendly approach, simple to manage accounts of the customers etc. all such positive options has place a negative impact on the employment of traditional banking services. This analysis relies upon the first furthermore as secondary study. so as to arrive at the sample size, non-chance technique has been used. For the first knowledge collection the structured pre tested form is employed to record the response of varied respondents. Secondary knowledge has been collected from annual reports, different revealed literature of the banks etc. knowledge is collected from fifty three respondents for the aim of crucial the impact of internet banking on the standard banking services. All things were measured by responses

on a Five-Point Likert Scale in agreement/relevance with statements, starting from 1= stronglyDisagree/ utterly impertinent to 5=Strongly Agree/Completely Relevant. The reliableness of data has been tested through Cranach Alpha. It's additional been analyzed those ' t-test and percentages. The analysis of primary knowledge was distributed victimization applied math Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) twenty. The results of the study prove that web banking incorporates a significant impact on the standard banking services

1. INTRODUCTION

The advancement in info technology provides a great deal of advantages yet as challenges tothe industry and its customers. Antecedently customers so as to finish bankingtransactions ought to visit branch in person however with the help of net banking currently customerscan complete their banking transactions while not creating personal visit to the branch. Banks are now victimisation websites so as to show the list of product and services that are provided to itscustomers. net banking offers a range of services to the shoppers like accessing accountdetails, funds transfer, and interbank transfers to accounts with different banks, request for gap abank account, utility bill payments etc. it's a proposal that facilitates the shoppers to hold outtheir banking activities from their desktop,supportedby theability and simple thenet.Today thenet banking isn't solely fashionable in huge cities or urban areas however additionally becomingfamous within the rural areas.The stunning advantages that net banking is providing to its customers force them to shiftfrom ancient banking services to the fashionable banking services like net banking, mobilebanking, ATM's etc.net banking has not helped the services customers to avail banking by simply sitting in their homes.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the Impact of web banking on the purchasers.
2. To study the explanations of web banking adoption among the purchasers.
3. Comparative study of Net Banking Facility of the Banks

Limitation of the study:

The present study is predicated upon the results of survey conducted on solely fifty three respondents. The results of the study are subject to the constraints of sample size, regional territory, psychological, financial and emotional characteristics of surveyed population. Because of such limitations the study cannot be generalized.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Type of Research

This study is DESCRIPTIVE in nature. It helps in breaking imprecise drawback into smaller and precise drawback and emphasizes on discovering of latest ideas and insights.

Data collection:

This analysis is predicated upon the first in addition as secondary study. so as to reach the sample size, non-likelihood technique has been used. For the first knowledge assortment the structured pre tested form is employed to record the response of assorted respondents. Knowledge is collected from fifty three respondents for the aim of determinant the impact of web banking on the traditional banking services. All things were measured by responses on a Five-Point Likert Scale in agreement/relevance with statements, starting from 1= powerfully agree/ completely relevant to 5=Strongly disagree/Completely inapplicable. The sources used for secondary data collection includes analysis papers, articles, websites of banks, knowledge revealed by run batted in.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

The dependableness of knowledge has been tested through Cronbach Alpha, it's any been analyzed thought-test and share. The analysis of primary knowledge was administrated victimisation Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) twenty. For the hypothesis development for the study null hypothesis has been developed that provides that the net banking has no significant impact on the normal banking services

Impact on banking services:

1. Ease of comfort
2. Facilitates Any time Anywhere banking
3. Faster and better services.
4. Regular updated information

1. Profile of the respondent

Gender

Male	114
Female	36
Total	150

Interpretation:

The result shows that majority of respondents i.e. seventy six area unit males United Nations agency area unit mistreatment the E-banking services and pure gold area unit the female United Nations agency area unit mistreatment E-banking services. feminine are not mistreatment this service as a result of they have less data regarding the online which they trust face to face interaction a lot of. Thus it shows that E-banking is a lot of notable among male.

2. Age

Age	Total no
Below 20	34
21-30	40
31-40	32
41-50	27
Above 50	17

Interpretation:

The result shows that majority of respondent i.e. 27% falls below the class of 21-30 years and 34 % falls below 20 years it shows that E-Banking is

very known among children as they are the most users of E-Banking and list comes below higher than fifty years.

3. Occupation

Occupation	Total no
Government	37
Private	40
Business	48
Others	25
Total	150

Interpretation:

The result shows that Majority of respondent that area unit victimization E-Banking area unit bourgeois i.e. thirty second they are victimization E-Banking services as a result of it finish within the time saving.

4.Income

Income	Total no
Below 10,000	23
10,000-25000	48
25000-50000	45
More than 50000	34
Total	150

Interpretation:

From the available table it seen that 48 Respondents are under Rs .25000 income and 45 Respondents are above Rs.25000 income group.

Q.1) Do you think E-Banking administrations is vital right now?

Yes	135
No	15
Total	150

Interpretation:

To make work easiest E-Banking facility are very useful and necessary in present scenario.

Q.2) In which bank do you have your account ?

Option	No.of respondent
Icici	39
Kotak	24
Both	87
Total	150

Interpretation:

According to this study majority of respondent i.e.58% have their accounts in each banks ICICI AND KOTAK bank and 16 PF respondent have their account kotak bank therefore it suggests that an outsize no. of respondent have expertise in each banks.

Q.3) while opening up the accounts, where you mindful of E-Banking administrations gave by your bank

Option	No .of respondent
Yes	109
No	41

Interpretation:

According to this survey majority of respondent i.e.73% were tuned in to E-banking services provided by their bank and twenty seventh of respondent weren't tuned in to the E-banking services provided by their bank at the time of gap from their account because of lack of awareness and some are victimisation banking services from last various years at that time bank wasn't giving E-Banking service so as that they weren't aware at that time however currently they are aware.

Q.4) It is safe to say that you are Availing E-Banking administrations?

Option	No of respondent
Yes	96
No	13

Interpretation:

The result shows that half a mile respondent UN agency square measure responsive to E-Banking they are availing E-Banking services and 12-tone system are not availing E-Banking services nevertheless they are responsive to E-Banking the explanation that they still have religion in ancient banking.

Q.5) which of the accompanying E-Banking administrations would you say you ismindful of?

Options	No of respondent
Internet banking	49
Mobile banking	97
Phone banking	67
Online banking	12
Debit card	102
Others	21

Interpretation:

Only 15-20 % folksquare measure wish to change their bank for victimization e-banking service.in this figure most square measure the client square measure related to ICICI bank and in line with Maine solely reason square measure behind typicallythis can be} often Non educated persons that they are don't data concerning the E-Banking process.

5. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

1. In this study not included with other banks.
2. This isdepending only on ICICI and KOTAK.
3. In this study based only comparative data of ICICI and KOTAK bank.
4. This study is not included other banks facilities.

6. SUGGESTIONS:

- 1 Rural percentage is very low.
- 2 Lesser no of branches compare with other competitors.
- 3 Make the banking process easily for customers.
- 4 More no of customer have account with private banks.
- 5 Number of problem faced by the people is more in public sector bank.
- 6 People are more satisfied from the private sector banks due to their better services provided by them.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper provides that the continual and increasing use of web banking has place a negativeimpact on the employment of ancient banking services by the shoppers. thanks to the convenience, ease,fast, better, user friendly approach, price advantageous, atmosphere friendly approach, regular upto date data,

banking apply of constructing on-line system most secure, 24/7 service, hassle free services, time saving etc. area unit the motivating factors that area unit promoting the usagerate of web banking customers and to use additional and additional web banking for his or her regular banking services whether or not these services involves basic banking services like checking of accountor to request for varied banking facilities and conjointly price extra services like fund transfer, payment of utility bills, payment of mastercard bills etc. thanks to all such options web banking is turning into a substitute of assorted ancient banking services. The hypothesis developed in this paper is accepted that web banking features a negative impact on the standard banking services.